

A Simple Synthesis of 4-Carboxyatractyligenin from Atractyligenin[†]

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Protection of atractyligenin (**1**) as the tris-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl derivative allows carboxylation at C(4) to give after mild acidic treatment 4-carboxyatractyligenin (**3**). This simple and convenient procedure is recommended for α -carboxylation of other polyfunctional carboxylic acids.

The thistle *Atractylis gummifera*, known since ancient times for its deadly toxicity, produces two poisonous principles which are derivatives of diterpenoid atractyligenin, **1**¹. These substances, atractyloside (**2**) and 4-carboxyatractyloside, function by blocking the transport of adenosine diphosphate (ADP) into mitochondria, thereby decreasing ATP production¹⁻³. Atractylosides also occur in the coffee plants *Coffea arabica* and *Coffea robusta*⁴. Earlier reports from this laboratory have described two total synthetic routes to **1**⁵. Presented herein is a simple method for the synthesis of 4-carboxyatractyligenin (**3**) from atractyligenin (**1**).

Atractyligenin (**1**) was converted quantitatively into its *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl (TBS) ester-bis-TBS ether by reaction in methylene chloride with 6-8 equiv of 2,6-lutidine and 4.5 equiv of TBS triflate at 0° for 10 min, and the product was isolated simply by filtration through a short plug of silica gel and removal of solvent. Sequential treatment of the product in THF solution with 2 equiv of lithium

diisopropylamide at -78° and excess CO₂ afforded a crude 4-carboxylation product (**4**) which was isolated and exposed to 10% aqueous hydrofluoric acid in acetonitrile to afford after chromatography on silica gel 4-carboxyatractyligenin (**3**) in 40% overall yield from **1**. Treatment of synthetic **3** with excess of ethereal diazomethane at 0° furnished after isolation and chromatography on silica gel the dimethyl ester **5**, the spectra of which were identical with those reported⁶. The success of the convenient synthesis of **3** from **1** which is described herein demonstrates the utility of labile TBS esters in carboxylation substrate reactions even in the case of a sterically encumbered substrate.

Experimental

Conversion of 1 to 3 and 5 via 4: To a suspension of atractyligenin **1** (10 mg, 0.0312 mmol, 1 equiv) in dichloromethane at 0° was added 2,6-lutidine (22.5 mg, 25 μ l, 0.2102 mmol, 6.75 equiv) followed by *t*-butyldimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulphonate (37.2 mg, 33 μ l, 0.1407 mmol, 4.5 equiv). The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° for 10 min. The product was isolated by rapid filtration (dichloromethane) through a short plug of flash grade silica gel and removal of solvent as a colorless liquid (100%), which was used in the next step without further purification.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

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A solution of the above product in THF (500 μ l) was added to a solution of LDA (2 equiv, 0.0624 mmol, 6.7 mg), at -78° in THF (500 μ l). LDA was prepared by sequential addition of diisopropylamine (7 mg, 9.7 ml, 0.0691 mmol, 2.2 equiv) and *n*-butyllithium (4 mg, 0.0624 mmol, 2 equiv, 41.6 μ l of 1.5 M in hexane) to THF (500 μ l) at -20° for 20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at -78° for 2 h and then treated with a stream of dry CO₂ at -78° for 5 min. The resulting mixture was poured onto cold saturated aqueous sodium chloride and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 \times 15 ml). The organic layers were combined and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was used without further purification in the next step.

The above carboxylation product (4) was dissolved in acetonitrile (400 μ l) and then treated with 10% aqueous HF solution (300 μ l)³. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° for 1 h and 22° for 3 h. Silica gel chromatography (3 : 3 : 40 : 50 acetic acid-methanol-ethyl acetate-ether) provided pure carboxyatractyligenin 3 (4.5 mg, 40%); tlc (3 : 3 : 40 : 50 acetic acid-methanol-ethyl acetate-ether) : $R_f = 0.40$; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 5.16 (1H, s), 5.05 (1H, s), 4.12 (1H, m), 3.76 (1H, bs), 2.69 (1H, t, J 3.2 Hz), 2.50 (1H, dd, J 12.1, 2.6 Hz), 2.16 (1H, dd, J 11.8, 4.2 Hz), 1.89 (1H, d, J 11.3 Hz), 1.83–1.71 (3H, m, including 1.78 (1H, bs, D₂O exchangeable)), 1.64 (1H, t, J 12.1 Hz), 1.48–1.43 (3H, m), 1.36 (1H, dd, J 11.3, 3.2 Hz), 1.10 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 1.03 (3H, s), 0.76 (1H, t, J 11.8 Hz); FTIR ν_{\max} (neat) 3354, 1685, 1572, 1368, 1355, 1239, 1037 cm⁻¹; FAB MS (xenon, glycerol) 409 (M-1+2Na)⁺, 365 (M+1)⁺, 363 (M-1)⁺, 347.

To a solution of carboxyatractyligenin (3) in methanol was added excess of diazomethane at 0° . The mixture was then concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (1 : 4 ethyl acetate-ether) to give carboxyatractyligenin methyl ester 5 which was spectroscopically identical with the diester of natural 3⁶.

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